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Capsule Hotels: The Intersection of Design and Functionality

Kapsül Oteller: Tasarım ve İşlevselliğin Buluşması

ABSTRACT

The tourism sector, transformed under the influence of globalization, has paved the way for the development of new and alternative accommodation types alongside traditional lodging methods. Capsule hotels, which have gained prominence during this transformation, stand out with their modern and minimalist designs, offering innovative solutions for the efficient use of limited space, particularly in densely populated metropolitan areas. Originating in Japan and rapidly spreading globally, this type of accommodation has been developed in response to individuals' evolving lifestyles, rapidly changing work and travel habits, and the growing need for short-term and affordable stays. Typically consisting of compact, single-person sleeping capsules, these units are equipped with essential amenities such as a bed, electrical outlet, lighting, ventilation, and in some cases, a television, providing users with both privacy and functionality. In addition to personal spaces, capsule hotels are supported by shared facilities including showers, toilets, lounges, work areas, and laundry services. Characterized by a minimalist approach, these structures are particularly favored by backpackers, digital nomads, solo travelers, and individuals on short business trips. This study examines global examples of capsule hotels, aiming to analyze their architectural and functional features, design principles, influence on user preferences, and their position within the tourism sector. Based on a comprehensive literature review and employing qualitative content analysis, the research reveals the contributions of capsule hotels to contemporary accommodation practices and highlights their potential for future development.

Keywords: Tourism, Accommodation, Design, Interior Architecture, Futurism

ÖZET

Küreselleşmenin etkisiyle dönüşen turizm sektörü, geleneksel konaklama biçimlerinin yanı sıra yeni ve alternatif konaklama türlerinin gelişimine zemin hazırlamıştır. Bu dönüşüm sürecinde öne çıkan kapsül oteller, modern ve minimalist tasarımlarıyla dikkat çekmekte; özellikle nüfus yoğunluğu yüksek metropollerde sınırlı alanların verimli kullanımına yönelik yenilikçi çözümler sunmaktadır. Japonya'da ortaya çıkan ve kısa sürede küresel ölçekte yaygınlaşan bu otel tipi, bireylerin değişen yaşam biçimlerine, hızla dönüşen çalışma ve seyahat alışkanlıklarına, kısa süreli ve ekonomik konaklama ihtiyaçlarına yanıt verecek şekilde geliştirilmiştir. Genellikle tek kişilik uyku kapsülleri şeklinde düzenlenen bu kompakt alanlar; yatak, priz, aydınlatma, havalandırma ve bazı örneklerde televizyon gibi temel donanımlarla donatılmakta, kullanıcıya hem mahremiyet hem de işlevsellik sunmaktadır. Kapsül oteller, bireysel kullanım alanlarının yanı sıra duş, tuvalet, oturma ve çalışma alanları ile çamaşırhane gibi ortak kullanıma açık mekânlarla desteklenmektedir. Minimalist yaklaşımıyla öne çıkan bu yapılar, özellikle sırt çantalı gezginler, dijital göçebeler, yalnız seyahat eden bireyler ve kısa süreli iş seyahatine çıkan kullanıcılar tarafından tercih edilmektedir. Bu çalışma, kapsül otellerin dünya genelindeki örneklerini inceleyerek; bu konaklama modelinin mimari ve işlevsel açıdan taşıdığı özellikleri, tasarım prensiplerini, kullanıcı eğilimleri üzerindeki etkilerini ve turizm sektöründeki yerini analiz etmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Literatür taramasına dayalı olarak nitel içerik analizi yöntemiyle yürütülen araştırma, kapsül otellerin çağdaş konaklama anlayışına sunduğu katkıları ve gelecekteki potansiyelini ortaya koymaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Turizm, Konaklama, Tasarım, İç Mimarlık, Fütürizm

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is defined as the act of individuals temporarily travelling to a location different from their usual residence for purposes such as relaxation, entertainment, cultural experiences, or work-related activities, during which they stay in accommodations provided at the destination. According to the Turkish Language Association (TDK,2024), tourism encompasses "all economic, cultural, and technical measures and efforts undertaken to attract tourists to a country or region." Tourism activities generate significant income for local communities through economic, social, and cultural interactions in the regions visited.

While there are various accommodation types in tourism, including hotels, motels, resorts, and hostels, hotels remain the most widely used form. The term "hotel," derived from the French word "hôtel," refers to establishments where individuals fulfill their accommodation, dining, and other basic needs during travel. According to the Regulation on the Certification and Qualification of Tourism Facilities (2005), hotels are defined as facilities primarily aimed at meeting the accommodation needs of their customers. In addition to this core function, they often incorporate auxiliary and complementary units for dining, sports, and entertainment activities.

Hotels vary based on the needs and budgets of individuals. Accommodation options tailored to diverse requirements include hotels, hostels, motels, and campgrounds. Hotels are categorized based on their comfort levels into single-star, two-star, three-star, four-star, and five-star establishments. Additionally, they are divided into specific types, including city hotels, concept hotels, boutique hotels, thermal hotels, ski hotels (for winter tourism), and eco-friendly hotels (Penner, Adams, & Robson, 2013, s. 7). In recent years, capsule hotels have emerged as a new category within this classification.

Throughout history, people have traveled for purposes such as exploration, art, military campaigns, religion, or trade. During their journeys, travelers have sought affordable, simple, and functional accommodation options. Over time, various forms of lodging have developed to address these needs across different historical periods and cultures. In ancient cities like Corinth in Greece, numerous establishments provided travelers with not only food and drink but also a place to sleep. During the Roman Empire, "tabernae" and "caupona" served as key lodging options. While "tabernae" operated as inns or taverns within cities, "caupona" was located outside towns and provided basic lodging for travelers. Additionally, "mansiones," a type of inns, were strategically positioned along Roman roads to accommodate those traveling for government or commercial purposes (Hotel,2024).

The medieval revival of trade in Europe led to the widespread growth of inns and lodging houses. Simple monastery guesthouses were also available, designed to meet the basic needs of travelers. The second half of the 18th century in Europe, often referred to as the "Golden Age of Travel," marked a period when affluent families sent their children abroad for education. Countries like France, Italy, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, and Ireland became popular destinations, with accommodations, transportation, and rest facilities emerging as profitable business opportunities, laying the foundation for the modern tourism industry (Hotel,2024).

Marco Polo, during the 13th century, encountered an extensive relay and lodging system in China used as stopovers for travelers and Mongol postal services. In both Asia and Western Europe, inns tailored for merchants became common during the late Middle Ages. In Japan, "shukudo" offered basic accommodation designed for visitors to temples, while "ronin" provided temporary lodging for samurais. These spaces were minimalist in design, reflecting the prioritization of essential needs. Nishiyama Onsen Keiunkan, constructed in 705 AD, is recognized as the world's oldest hotel in its current sense (Atlas Obscura. n.d.).

In India, "dharmashalas" and "sarai" were established to cater to the basic needs of travelers, often for religious purposes, at minimal costs. Additionally, floating accommodations utilized during sea voyages exemplify efficient use of limited space. Within Turkish and Islamic cultures, particularly in Anatolia, inns and caravanserais played significant roles as travel lodges. For example, the "Elçiler Hanı" in Ottoman Istanbul, which housed European envoys during their official visits, provides insights into the lodging requirements of work-related travelers. Flemish envoy Busbecq described the rooms in his memoirs as resembling small, modestly furnished monastic cells, designed solely to meet essential needs without any focus on luxury or elegance.

As evident from these historical accounts, accommodation solutions in the past primarily focused on fulfilling the fundamental human need for shelter, often emphasizing minimalist and functional designs. Numerous examples of lodging spaces dedicated to travel purposes can be found throughout history.

In today's globalized world, innovations in travel and accommodation spaces are shaped by user needs and preferences. One such innovation is the emergence of capsule hotels, characterized by their minimalist designs.

Introduced as an innovative product in tourism over the past two decades, capsule hotels are founded on the concept of providing accommodation in limited-space capsules. The primary target market for capsule hotels consists of budget-conscious, short-term travelers, often younger adventurers, who prioritize cost-effective lodging and accept the limited hospitality services offered (Çalhan, 2023, s. 113).

Developed in line with the characteristics of Japanese urbanization, "capsule hotels are often located near train stations in city centers to serve businesspeople who miss the last train" (Yu & Akita, 2019, s. 384). Unlike traditional hotels, "capsule hotels comprise a series of small, bed-equipped rooms or units designed to offer low-cost and convenient overnight stays. These hotels are typically found in metropolitan areas and near airport terminals" (Chen & Wei, 2022, s. 1). In modern airport terminals, capsule hotels also cater to transit passengers who require sleeping and resting facilities during extended layovers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sleeping Pods at Istanbul Airport and Moscow Sheremetyevo Airport, **Resources** Refundor (n.d.).

The increasing number of capsule hotels can be attributed to their lower accommodation costs compared to hostels, making them a preferred choice for both business travelers and young adventurers (Yu, 2019, s. 384). Also referred to as "pod hotels," capsule hotels are defined as "small-sized accommodations providing at least one bed for a tourist to sleep or rest" (Chen & Wei, 2022, s. 1). These hotels typically consist of single-occupancy units designed as compact, cost-effective spaces equipped to meet the basic needs of guests. The development of capsule hotels as we know them today is undeniably linked to the architectural influence of Kisho Kurokawa's Nakagin Capsule Tower. Completed in 1972, the tower comprised 140 prefabricated self-contained capsules integrated into two concrete towers of 11 and 13 stories, respectively.

Each capsule measured 2.5 m × 2.5 m × 4.0 m and functioned as a small residential or office space, complete with a bathroom (Figure 2). The capsules provided a small yet functional living area designed to meet essential needs. Features such as beds, power outlets, and lighting—commonly found in modern capsule hotels—were also present in the Nakagin capsules. The Nakagin Capsule Tower focused on maximizing the efficient use of limited space, particularly in dense urban centers. This concept has significantly influenced the placement of capsule hotels in busy city centers and airport terminals. However, a fundamental difference lies in the intended function: while the Nakagin Tower was designed primarily as a permanent residential and workspace solution, capsule hotels have evolved to address the specific needs of short-term travelers. The customization of capsule hotels to meet the requirements of the hospitality sector marks a key point of divergence from the Nakagin Tower.

Figure 2. Floor Plan and General View of the Living Unit in the Nakagin Capsule Tower, **Resources** Wikimedia Commons (n.d.).

“The first capsule hotels, introduced in Osaka, Japan, were primarily constructed using plastic and glass materials” (Garda, 2020, s. 20). “The global market for capsule hotels reached a value of 167.07 million USD in 2017, with projections estimating it to grow to 272 million USD by the end of 2025” (Chen & Wei, 2022, s. 1). Despite the significant anticipated growth of this accommodation trend globally, the existing literature reveals a scarcity of studies on capsule hotels, underscoring the need for further research to enrich this field. The primary objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive literature review on capsule hotels—an emerging trend in accommodation that remains underexplored in academic research—and to examine their spatial and ergonomic characteristics. This research aims to address the evident gap in the literature on capsule hotels and contribute valuable insights to this under-researched topic. Consequently, the study is considered significant and valuable for its potential to fill a notable void in the academic discourse surrounding capsule hotels.

2. THE CONCEPT OF CAPSULE HOTELS

Capsule hotels are spaces designed to meet the short-term accommodation needs of individuals. The concept of capsule hotels first gained popularity in Japan and has since been embraced in other countries. “In Japanese, capsule hotels are referred to as “カプセルホテル” (kapuseru hoteru). In regions such as China and Taiwan, these accommodations are known as “space capsule hotels,” “grid hotels,” or “energy-efficient youth hostels” (Ju Chena, 2020, s. 2). “The first capsule hotel, designed by architect Kisho Kurokawa, opened in Osaka in 1979” (Tiffany, 2022). This initial example, created specifically for businesspeople, accommodated only male guests. “The capsules measured 1.98 m x 0.90 m with a height of 0.76 m. Each capsule included small televisions, lighting, an alarm clock, and power outlets. Bathrooms were shared, and luggage was stored in lockers outside the capsules” (Capsule Inn Osaka. n.d.). Figure 3 presents images of the sleeping cabins and common areas of this first capsule hotel.

Figure 3. Capsules and Comfort Features of the First Capsule Hotel, Resources Sasaki, J (2024, May 2).

“The concept of a capsule hotel is a small room compartment typically the size of a single bed constructed from materials such as fibreglass, plastic, wood, metal, or any other rigid substance” (Qiu, 2022, s. 125). Drawing inspiration from terms like “pod” and “capsule,” these hotels emphasize minimalism and futuristic design, offering innovative accommodation solutions. Initially introduced as a proposal to address the rest needs of workers with demanding routines before starting a new workday, capsule hotels are distinguished from other types of lodging by their space-efficient designs. “Traditionally, capsule hotels catered primarily to business professionals; however, many modern capsule hotels now accommodate female guests as well, incorporating gender-segregated floors or even separate buildings for men and women” (Capsule Hotels, 2024). “Given the tourism industry's broad range of products and services targeting diverse audiences, capsule hotels have emerged as an ideal accommodation option, particularly for adventurous and budget-conscious travelers” (Ju Chena et al., 2020, s. 1).

3. SPATIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CAPSULE HOTELS

The typical dimensions of a capsule are approximately” 1m × 2m × 1m, although some literature mentions the dimensions of 2m × 1.25m × 1m (Figure 4). Depending on their size, capsule hotels in Japan are designed to accommodate 50 to 700 guests within a single facility” (Jablonska et al., 2018, s. 242). A fundamental feature of capsule hotel design is space efficiency, which is why the design emphasizes minimalism and maximum functionality. Capsules are often stacked in double rows, circulation areas are minimized according to regulatory standards, and wet areas such as bathrooms are designed as shared spaces. The overarching goal is to optimize the number of guests who can be accommodated within the limited space.

Capsules typically include essential amenities such as beds, radios, clocks, lighting, safes for valuables, desks with power outlets, internet connectivity, and Wi-Fi. In addition to these features, shared spaces for guests are an integral part of capsule hotels, further enhancing their utility.

Figure 4. Sketch of a Capsule Unit, Resources Author's Archive.

3.1. Spatial Features of Capsules

Capsules in capsule hotels are designed with a minimalist approach, focusing on meeting the essential needs of guests. They provide practical solutions for short-term stays, ensuring functionality takes precedence over spaciousness. Although some users may perceive the limited space as inadequate, the design prioritizes efficiency and utility. With their futuristic and compact layouts, capsule hotels have significantly contributed to the evolution and popularity of modern accommodation concepts. This approach also enhances the preference of decision-makers in terms of spatial sustainability and efficiency.

A standard capsule measures approximately 1 meter in width, 2 meters in length, and 1 meter in height, typically accommodating a single futon bed. While fibreglass is a common construction material, other materials and designs may vary depending on the specific concept. Capsules are often arranged in double-stacked configurations, aligned side by side along corridors (Capsule Hotels, 2024).

Due to the materials used and safety regulations, capsules generally have high sound permeability. As a result, loud noises are prohibited in capsule areas to ensure a quiet environment. Capsules typically include essential amenities such as bed linens, blankets, pillows, internet connectivity, radios, alarm clocks, ventilation systems, lighting, power outlets, and televisions. Privacy features such as curtains, blinds, or shutters are also common, although the specific amenities may vary between hotels.

Ergonomics plays a critical role in capsule design. For instance, in a typical capsule, an average-height man can sit upright with approximately 10 cm of headspace remaining, offering sufficient room for temporary seating. However, sitting in capsules is generally a transient activity. The confined space may feel claustrophobic to some users, highlighting the importance of interior design strategies to mitigate such perceptions. Design elements such as thoughtful use of lighting, color schemes, and textures can help create a more comfortable and visually spacious experience. In addition to traditional capsule designs, some modern hotels offer units resembling small private rooms. “Furthermore, advancements in technology have enabled newer capsules to incorporate futuristic features, resembling space capsules and offering a variety of innovative amenities” (Tiffany, 2022).

3.2. Usage and Spatial Characteristics of Shared Areas

Capsule hotels provide individuals with minimal personal space, primarily intended for sleeping.

All other functions, such as bathing, dining, and relaxation, are facilitated in shared spaces. Bathrooms, toilets, and showers are typically communal and designed to be used by multiple guests. Many capsule hotels feature spacious shared bathing areas, allowing guests to enjoy a hot bath before retiring to their capsules. Additional amenities in these hotels often include restaurants, vending machines, laundry facilities, internet kiosks, lounges, entertainment rooms, gaming areas, or manga libraries (Capsule Hotels, 2024).

“Shared spaces in capsule hotels are often segregated by gender. While some establishments have introduced separate elevators and rooms for men and women, fire safety and other operational considerations require that all capsule doors be easily accessible from both sides” (Qiu, 2022, p. 130-131). “In a typical capsule

hotel layout, toilets are located at the end of corridors, and a common bathroom area may serve all guests” (Go Tokyo, 2020).

Upon arrival at capsule hotels, guests are usually provided with personal care products for use during their stay. Guests are often required to leave their shoes and large belongings in designated communal areas before entering the capsule zone, where movement is restricted to slippers. These rules aim to maintain noise control and hygiene. A key principle in capsule hotel sleeping areas is the enforcement of silence, as the capsules’ high sound permeability can easily disrupt other guests. The thoughtful design of shared spaces is essential for maintaining guest satisfaction in capsule hotels. The functionality and cleanliness of communal areas significantly influence the overall user experience. Enhanced hygiene standards, efficient layouts, and ergonomic designs are critical components for ensuring that these spaces meet the needs of a diverse range of guests.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study aims to explore the innovative contributions and designs of capsule hotels, a relatively under-researched topic, and identify the fundamental spatial characteristics of capsules offered in internationally recognized capsule hotels. To achieve this, the research employed a qualitative content analysis approach, primarily focusing on a literature review and the examination of capsule hotel websites.

Between April 15, 2024, and May 27, 2024, online platforms such as TripAdvisor, Booking.com, Expedia.com, Agoda.com, Hotels.com, and Trivago.com were searched using keywords like "capsule," "hostel," "pod," "hub," and "kep." Based on user reviews, media coverage, and listings, seven capsule hotels with five-star ratings and frequent mentions in travel blogs were selected for analysis. Additionally, a capsule hotel located at Sabiha Gökçen Airport in Turkey was physically inspected and documented.

The study also included a review of international and national publications covering news articles and reports on capsule hotels, as well as analyses of the "best capsule hotels" around the world. The official websites of the selected capsule hotels were examined to evaluate the features and services offered, and findings were analyzed using qualitative content analysis techniques.

Furthermore, the research incorporated traveler experiences by reviewing videos and travel blogs that document stays at capsule hotels. These observations contributed to a broader understanding of user experiences and preferences, helping to address gaps in the literature.

By combining data from various sources, this study aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of capsule hotels, highlighting their spatial and ergonomic features. Given the limited existing research, this work is expected to significantly contribute to addressing the knowledge gap on capsule hotels and provide insights for future studies in this domain.

4.1. Case Studies

This study includes analyses of capsule hotels operating across different continents and countries, featuring diverse designs and concepts. The selected hotels represent modern examples of this innovative accommodation trend. Below are the details of the capsule hotels examined in this research.

4.1.1. First Cabin Hotels, Tokyo, Japan

First Cabin Hotels operates ten facilities in Japan, offering a variety of accommodation options. These include four distinct cabin types: first-class cabins (2.10 m × 2.10 m × 2.10 m), business-class cabins (1.20 m × 2.10 m × 2.10 m), premium economy-class capsules (1.20 m × 2.10 m × 1 m), and premium-class cabins (Figure 5; 6; 7). None of these cabins includes private bathrooms or toilets; guests are required to use shared facilities. For safety reasons, cabins cannot be locked, and entryways are covered with curtains, except for premium-class cabins, which offer lockable doors. Each capsule features amenities such as a locked drawer, digital safe, lighting, USB ports, electrical outlets, and a television, which must be used with headphones to avoid disturbing other guests. While premium-class cabins can accommodate multiple guests, other types are strictly single-occupancy. Shared spaces are gender-segregated (First Cabin, 2024). Figures 8 and 9 sleeping spaces in First Cabin Capsules.

Figures 5, 6, and 7. The Features and Layouts of First Cabin Capsules, **Resources** First Cabin. (2024).

Figure 8-9. First Cabin Capsules, **Resources** First Cabin (2024).

4.3. Cityhub Hotel, Netherlands

CityHub Hotel first opened in Amsterdam in 2015, offering 50 capsule rooms. It expanded to Rotterdam in 2018 with 126 capsules, and to Copenhagen in 2020 with 210 capsules and five rooms. These hotels are designed to reflect principles of sustainability and sharing. Capsules are demountable and can be reassembled at different locations. Made from recycled materials, the energy-efficient capsules minimize each traveler's carbon footprint. Capsules accommodate up to two people and feature king-size beds, USB ports, ventilation systems, and smoke detectors. Using the hotel's proprietary "CityHosts" app, guests can control capsule lighting and other settings, including adjusting the light color. Secure lockers are located in shared spaces, as capsules do not include safes. The hotel does not accept pets or children under the age of four (CityHub, 2024). Figures 10 and 11 illustrate the capsule designs in CityHub hotels.

Figure 10-11. CityHub Capsules, **Resources** CityHub (2024).

4.4. Kepler Club, Sabiha Gökçen Airport, Turkey

Kepler Club, located in the international terminal of Sabiha Gökçen Airport, is recognized as Turkey's first capsule hotel. It is designed to offer a peaceful and minimalist environment amidst the busy airport setting. Capsules, referred to as “Kep” units, measure 2.20 m × 1.40 m × 1.10 m and feature ergonomically designed beds, climate control systems, televisions, adjustable reading lights, mirrors, secure lockers, and small work desks. The capsules are soundproof and environmentally friendly. Shared areas include showers, smart toilets, dressing rooms, and lounges. While capsules and wet areas are gender-segregated, shared lounges and seating areas are available to all guests. Complementary tea and coffee are provided in the common areas. The facility does not accommodate children under the age of seven (Kepler Club, 2024). Figures 12, 13, 14, and 15 present visuals of the Kepler Club capsules.

Figure 12. Kepler Club Capsule Model, Resources Kepler Club (2024).

Figure 13-14-15. Kepler Club Capsules, Resources Author's Archive.

4.5. 9h Nine Hours Suidobashi, Tokyo

Located in Tokyo's Chiyoda district, Nine Hours Suidobashi operates on the concept of "nine hours": one hour for showering, seven hours for sleeping, and one hour for getting ready. Capsules have a pod-like design with smooth corners, creating a cocoon-like sleeping environment. Each capsule measures 1.10 m × 2.20 m × 1.10 m and features adjustable lighting and power outlets. A sleep environment control system enhances the user experience. Shared spaces, including locker rooms, are gender-segregated, and lockers

measure 36 cm × 52 cm × 200 cm. The facility does not accommodate children under the age of six (Nine Hours, 2024). Figures 16 and 17 depict the layout and features of Nine Hours capsules.

Figure 16-17. 9h Nine Hours Capsules, Resources Nine Hours (2024).

4.6. Book and Bed Tokyo, Shinjuku

Located in Shinjuku, Tokyo, this capsule hotel features a library concept. Sleeping spaces are integrated into bookshelves, offering a unique experience for guests. Capsules measure 0.95 m × 2 m and provide basic amenities such as beds, electrical outlets, safes, and light controls. Superior rooms feature king-size beds measuring 1.90 m × 2 m and are more private, with curtains separating them from shared spaces. Communal areas include reading spaces and dining facilities (Book and Bed Tokyo, 2024). Figures 18 and 19 showcase the library-style sleeping spaces.

Figure 18-19. Book and Bed Capsules Resources Book and Bed Tokyo (2024).

4.7. The Millennials Shibuya, Tokyo

Located in Tokyo's Shibuya district, The Millennials offers two capsule types: "Smartpods" and "Theaterpods." Smartpods feature a 3 m² area with a comfortable bed, while Theaterpods include an 80-inch screen and a projector. Theaterpods also feature adjustable electric beds and under-bed storage. Capsules include alarm systems, projectors, safes, electrical outlets, and lighting. Guests can control pod settings via an iPod provided during check-in. Shared spaces include kitchens, lounges, and gaming areas, accounting for 20% of the hotel's total space. The hotel does not admit guests under 18 years of age, or pets (Lively Hotels, 2024). Figures 20, 21, and 22 highlight the design of The Millennials capsules.

Figure 20- 21. The Millennials Capsules Resources Lively Hotels (2024).

Figure 22. The Millennials Floor Plan **Resources** Lively Hotels (2024).

4.8. Space Night Capsule Hostel, Berlin

This space-themed capsule hostel in Berlin offers single and double capsules, with sizes ranging from 3 m² to 5 m². Capsules are equipped with beds, safes, climate control, smoke detectors, reading lights, mirrors, foldable desks, and power outlets. Capsules are enclosed with doors for added privacy. Communal areas include shared toilets and bathrooms. Unlike other capsule hotels, this facility does not offer shared kitchens, dining, or lounge spaces (Space Night Capsule Hostel, 2024). Figure 23 shows the space-themed capsules at Space Night Capsule Hostel.

Figure 23. Space Night Capsule Hostel Capsules **Resources** Space Night Capsule Hostel (2024)

5. FINDINGS

The findings from the case studies are summarized under five subheadings:

5.1. Design Features of Capsule Hotels

Capsule hotels are designed to maximize the efficient use of limited spaces while meeting the needs of modern users. Standard features include lighting, power outlets, USB ports, lockable storage, ventilation systems, televisions, alarms, smoke detectors, and mirrors (Table 1). Despite their compact nature, these features provide essential comfort for guests.

5.2. User Experiences and Perceptions

Some users report experiencing claustrophobia due to the confined spaces within capsules. The absence of private toilets and bathrooms necessitates shared usage among guests, highlighting hygiene as a critical concern in such accommodations.

5.3. Advantages of Capsule Hotels

The primary advantages of capsule hotels are their minimal space requirements and cost-effectiveness. With their technological and comfortable designs, capsule hotels are increasingly preferred by backpackers, business travelers, and those seeking unique accommodation experiences. They offer a more appealing alternative to hostels for budget-conscious travelers.

5.4. Disadvantages of Capsule Hotels

The limited space within capsules imposes physical constraints, and the lack of privacy is a notable drawback. Privacy is typically ensured using curtains, but sound isolation remains an issue, with noises being audible both inside and outside the capsules. Additionally, the absence of designated changing areas highlights the need for specific spaces where guests can comfortably dress. The communal nature of capsule hotels can pose challenges related to privacy, acoustics, and hygiene (Table 2). Furthermore, capsule hotels are often unsuitable for young children or guests with pets, making them less appealing to certain user groups.

5.5. Global Spread of Capsule Hotels

Originating in Japan, the concept of capsule hotels has expanded globally, becoming a popular trend in the accommodation sector. Capsule hotels are now recognized as an ideal option for short-term stays and business trips. The design principles of capsule hotels are being increasingly adopted in hostels, student dormitories, and youth centers, further promoting the concept globally (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Use of Capsule Sleeping Units in a Hostel Resources Project Archive. Design: Dilara Enise Şentürk (2025).

Table 1. Features of Capsule Hotels (Prepared by the author).

CAPSULE FEATURES	LIGHTING	SOCKET	TV	SAFE BOX	USB PORTS	VENTILATION	MIRROR	SMOKE DETECTOR	DOOR/ CURTAIN
CAPSULE HOTELS									
First Cabin Hotels Tokyo,Japan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CURTAIN
Cityhub Hotel, Netherlands	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	DOOR
Kepler Club, Turkey	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CURTAIN
9h Nine Hours Suidobashi, Tokyo	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	CURTAIN
Book and Bed, Tokyo,Shinjuku	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	CURTAIN
The Millennials Shibuya, Tokyo	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	CURTAIN
Space Night Capsule Hostel, Berlin	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	DOOR

Table 2. Individual and Collective Actions in Capsule Hotels (Prepared by the author).

INDIVIDUAL AND COLLECTIVE ACTIVITIES	SLEEPING AREA	CHANGING CABIN	COMMON AREAS	BATHROOM/ TOILET
CAPSULE HOTELS				
First Cabin Hotels Tokyo,Japan	210X210X210CM 120X210X210CM 120X210X100CM	✗	✓	SHARED
Cityhub Hotel, Netherlands	4 M ²	✗	✓	SHARED
Kepler Club, Turkey	140X220X110 CM	✗	✓	SHARED
9h nine hours Suidobashi Tokyo	110X220X110 CM	✗	✓	SHARED
Book and Bed, Tokyo, Shinjuku	95X200 CM 120X200 CM 190X200 CM	✗	✓	SHARED
The Millennials ,Shibuya, Tokyo	200X120X120	✗	✓	SHARED
Space Night Capsule Hostel, Berlin	5M2 3M2	✗	✗	SHARED

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Capsule hotels stand out as an innovative accommodation solution that combines minimal space usage, cost-effectiveness, and modern design principles in today's globalized world. Emerging from Japan, this concept has proven to be an ideal option for short-term stays and business trips, while its popularity continues to grow globally. The effective use of technology and the ability to address the changing needs of modern users have further contributed to the increasing preference for capsule hotels. However, limitations such as confined spaces and privacy issues remain key areas for improvement.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- **Design and Privacy:**

Improving sound insulation in capsule hotels is crucial for enhancing user satisfaction. The use of soundproof materials and innovative designs that optimize airflow could significantly improve comfort levels. The COVID-19 pandemic has also highlighted the importance of ventilation in shared spaces, emphasizing the need for careful attention to artificial ventilation in capsule hotel designs.

Privacy should be ensured by using more robust and secure closure systems instead of curtains, making capsule hotels more appealing to a broader audience.

- **User Experience and Ergonomics:**

To reduce the feeling of claustrophobia, interior design strategies could incorporate elements such as light, color, and textures that create a sense of openness. Detailed ergonomic designs should also be prioritized.

Small but private areas for guests to change clothes should be integrated into capsule hotel layouts to address the need for personal space.

- **Functionality of Shared Areas:**

Shared spaces such as bathrooms, showers, and lounges should be better organized to provide users with a sense of personal space. Hygienic measures should be emphasized in these areas, leveraging ergonomic, material, and technological design components.

Technological integrations, such as mobile apps for controlling lighting, temperature, and other features, could enhance the overall user experience.

- **Modular and Flexible Design:**

The modular structure of capsules highlights the importance of adaptability and flexibility in interior design. This approach aligns with the principles of flexible design in interior architecture, allowing capsule hotels to cater to different user profiles and regional requirements.

- **Minimalist Design Principles:**

Capsule hotels reflect a minimalist design philosophy, focusing on meeting basic needs without unnecessary details. Material selection, lighting, and color use should prioritize functionality while creating a spacious and organized atmosphere.

- **Sustainability and Energy Efficiency:**

Using sustainable and environmentally friendly materials in capsule hotels is essential for both economic and ecological sustainability. Incorporating recyclable materials and energy-saving systems can help reduce the environmental impact of these hotels.

- **Global Expansion of Capsule Hotels:**

While originating in Japan, capsule hotels have successfully expanded worldwide by adapting to different cultural needs. For instance, in Europe and the Middle East, greater emphasis on privacy, comfort, and security could better cater to local market demands.

Suggestions for future research can also be summarized as follows:

Despite their growing popularity, capsule hotels remain an underexplored topic in the literature. Future studies should investigate aspects such as customer satisfaction, operational costs, and long-term sustainability.

Quantitative and qualitative research on how users perceive capsule hotels in different regions could provide valuable insights for tailoring designs to cultural preferences.

The integration of technological advancements into capsule hotel designs should be studied further to enhance both user satisfaction and operational efficiency.

Capsule hotels represent an innovative design approach in interior architecture, developed with the goal of providing maximum functionality within minimal spaces. The design of these hotels incorporates fundamental principles of contemporary architecture, such as modularity, minimalism, and ergonomics, offering creative solutions tailored to user needs. From the perspective of interior architecture, capsule hotels serve as a significant source of inspiration for designing small spaces with creative solutions. In the design process, user comfort, functionality, and balance of aesthetics should be prioritized. Particularly, improvements in areas such as sound insulation, ergonomics, and privacy can significantly enhance both the user experience and the design quality of capsule hotels (Figure 25).

Figure 25. The Relationship of Design and Function in Capsule Hotels **Resources** Created by the author using artificial intelligence.

Capsule hotels, as a modern reflection of minimalism and modular design in interior architecture, represent a significant concept poised to shape the future of urban accommodation. Further research and development into their design details will enhance both user satisfaction and their success within the industry.

This study has examined the impact of capsule hotels on the tourism sector and accommodation design, highlighting their potential to become a leading trend in the future of lodging. By efficiently utilizing limited spaces, these hotels provide an economical and practical solution tailored to the evolving needs of modern users. However, improvements in areas such as sound insulation, privacy, and ergonomics are essential to make capsule hotels more widely accepted by a broader audience. Comprehensive academic research on capsule hotels is vital to strengthen their position both in the industry and in the academic literature. Such efforts will contribute to advancing this innovative lodging type and addressing the challenges associated with its design and functionality.

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